

Where is Lebanon going?

Analytical article | Hassan Mohammed Albaiti

The exchange rate of the lira between 1976 and 1990

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Since Lebanon's independence in 1943, it has witnessed local and international conflicts on its territory that did not end even in early 2022. With each conflict, the Lebanese lira groans because of the economic situation on the Lebanese street.

The deterioration of the Lebanese lira during the last three years at rates that exceeded imagination is reminiscent of the first moment of the devaluation of the Lebanese lira against the dollar, according to the database of the [Banque du Liban](#), as this is due to the events of 1975 when the Lebanese civil war broke out, and its developments continued over fifteen years, starting with the conflict between the leftists and the Palestinians on the one hand, and between the Maronite Christian bloc on the other, killing more than 120 thousand people, and the Lebanese lira at

this stage fell at a rate that moved from 2 to 4 liras against the US dollar.

With the second Israeli invasion of Beirut in 1982, and the Sabra and Shatila massacre, the value of the lira fell to five lira against the dollar, and then returned to settle at four lira after the May 17 agreement between the Lebanese and Israel.

But the defining moment after which the Lebanese lira did not know any stability was the uprising of February 6, 1984, which came as a rejection of this agreement by the House of Representatives, and the Palestinians, the Socialist Party and the Amal Movement were united in this uprising. During this uprising, the Syrian forces returned again to Lebanon with the return of this conflict.

The uprising ended with the Taif Agreement in 1989, but the Lebanese economy suffered losses as the Lebanese lira fell 88 times from 1984, reaching 530 against the dollar.

The deterioration of the lira did not stop at that time, because the Syrian army stormed the Republican Palace in Beirut in 1990, and expelled the commander of the Lebanese Army, Michel Aoun, in October of the same year, and here the deterioration was evident at a rate exceeding 30% during nine months of 1990, as the exchange rate reached 870 liras against the dollar.

With the ongoing turmoil in the Lebanese scene since the assassination of Rafik Hariri in 2005, and then the Second Lebanese-Israeli War in 2006, which affected the infrastructure of services, especially the electricity that the Lebanese suffer from until today due to [electrical rationing](#), and then the waste crisis of 2015, the lira had reached a level of remarkable collapse, scoring 1507 against the dollar.

However, 13 years after the second war, Lebanon was on a date with a new crisis in the history of its internal conflict, after Saad Hariri formed the new government in January 2019, which is supposed to lift Lebanon out of its plight in light of the tensions with Israel on the one hand, and with the Gulf countries on the other hand, those tensions caused by Hezbollah's weapons, but on the contrary, the spark of the crisis began with a failed assassination attempt on the Minister of State for Displaced Affairs, Saleh al-Gharib, in the areas of influence of the Socialist Party led by Walid Jumblatt. That incident stopped government meetings for six weeks since mid-2019, and then things settled after referring the assassination file to the Military Court, until forest fires broke out in Lebanon in mid-October of the same year.

With the outbreak of forest fires, the Lebanese street erupted at the same time with the emergence of popular uprisings after he ignited the decision of Communications Minister Mohamed Choucair to impose taxes on WhatsApp communications, ending the burning month of October with the resignation of the Hariri government, and the crisis of forming a new government began, which lasted for two months until Hassan Diab was named prime minister on December 20.

With the advent of Christmas in Lebanon, most Lebanese are no longer able to buy Eid gifts with the same purchasing power as before. The lira fell against the dollar to reach two thousand and three hundred, and cast a shadow over the needs of citizens, with the Lebanese banks taking a decision to prevent withdrawing in the dollar currency, and imposing illegal restrictions on transferring abroad. The customer is also given instead of the dollar the lira at its official exchange rate of 1,507 liras, as well as limiting the value of the withdrawal itself to reach the weekly withdrawal of only \$200, in a scene that shows the

deterioration of the banks' financial system after the October uprising.

With the year 2020, the Lebanese lira was with the two most prominent crises that the Lebanese street and world opinion did not expect, the Corona crisis and the explosion of the port of Beirut. The Lebanese opened the month of January with a week of anger against banking procedures and the collapse of the financial system, whose ceiling rose to reach the Lebanese government in March to announce the cessation of payment of Eurobonds, which are the debts owed to them equivalent to 1.2 billion US dollars.

With the state of closure and curfew caused by the Corona virus in most countries of the world, a third of workers in the private sector lost their jobs, and the salaries of others fell, in a scene that was not taken into account.

With the high cost of living and the Lebanese lira losing half its previous value by the end of 2019, the Lebanese street had a date for the third protest since October 2019.

In August, within minutes, all areas surrounding the port of Beirut were destroyed, which exploded as a result of the reaction of ammonium nitrate stored in its warehouses. Lebanon lost human lives and \$15 billion in material losses as a result of the damage caused by the explosion. With this explosion, Diab's government resigned, which failed to address the economic crisis.

After the explosion of the port of Beirut, and it was not possible to form a new government, French President Macron vowed to cut off financial support to Lebanon unless there were political and economic reforms in its system, and Eid brought Saad Hariri back to the political scene by forming a government

of 18 ministers, after four months of government paralysis that cast a shadow over the deteriorating lira, which reached a level of 8,500 liras against the dollar, ten times what it was in October 1990.

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 البورصة الدولية
 للمعلومات

جدول يبيّن ارتفاع حجم السيولة بالليرة اللبنانية خلال الأعوام 2010-2020.

التاريخ	حجم السيولة بالمليار ليرة	نسبة الارتفاع (%)
3 حزيران 2010	3,253	-
16 حزيران 2011	3,484	+ 7.1
7 حزيران 2012	3,828	+ 9.8
6 حزيران 2013	4,560	+ 19.1
5 حزيران 2014	4,911	+ 7.7
4 حزيران 2015	5,343	+ 8.8
2 حزيران 2016	8,876	+ 66.1
8 حزيران 2017	9,509	+ 7.1
7 حزيران 2018	10,897	- 1.4
6 حزيران 2019	10,736	-
4 حزيران 2020	24,999	+ 132.8

المصدر: تقارير مصرف لبنان.

During 2021, the Lebanese scene was unprecedentedly hot and tense at the political and economic levels, with poverty reaching three quarters of its population, according to the report of

the United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Western Asia (ESCWA), raising the rate of theft by 137% from 2020, as well as the rate of legal and illegal migration of more than 77,000 legal migrants, while the numbers of illegal migrants are not yet clear, according to studies and statistics conducted by the International Information Corporation.

With this painful scene in light of the budget deficit, the inflation resulting from the frequent printing of the currency, the aggravation of the electricity crisis, and the high cost of living, the lira fell unprecedentedly to reach 29 thousand lira in December 2021 against one dollar, and the [value of salaries for workers in the government and private sectors erodes with it.](#)

There are still many problems that the Lebanese economy suffers from, especially the new ones such as agricultural exports packed with drugs, which caused the Saudi boycott of Lebanese agricultural products at the time, and then the statements of the former Minister of Information in the government of Mikati "George Qardahi", which triggered a crisis at the political and economic levels between the Gulf and Lebanon, and the state of the political class when asked: **Where does Lebanon go?** The answer comes from its chief, Lebanese President Michel Aoun, who said: "Hell is on my mind once in a while."

جدول رقم 1: التراجع في رواتب الموظفين من الفئتين الخامسة والرابعة.

القيمة بالدولار حالياً	القيمة بالدولار سابقاً	الراتب الشهري بالليرة اللبنانية	الفئة - درجة
101	633	950 ألف	الخامسة - درجة 1
202	1,270	1.905 مليون	الخامسة - درجة 22
152	953	1.430 مليون	الرابعة - درجة 1
275	1,720	2.580 مليون	الرابعة - درجة 22

المصدر: الدولية للمعلومات استناداً إلى القانون الرقم 46 وإلى سعر صرف الدولار.